

D4.6 VISUALIZING AND DASH-BOARDING CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITIES BASED ON DIGITAL TWIN DATA

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ASHVIN has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 958161. This document reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project Title	Assistants for Healthy, Safe, and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin
Project Acronym	ASHVIN
Grant Agreement No	958161
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	LC-EEB-08-2020 - Digital Building Twins
Start Date of Project	1st October 2020
Duration of Project	36 Months

Name of the deliverable	Visualizing and dash-boarding construction activities based on digital twin data
Number of the deliverable	D4.6
Related WP number and name	WP 4 Control and real-time simulation of construction
Related task number and name	T4.6 Site control dashboard and Visualization
Deliverable dissemination level	PU
Deliverable due date	31-03-23
Deliverable submission date	31-03-23
Task leader/Main author	Rehan Khan (DTT)
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Reviewer(s)	Timo Hartmann (TUB), Paul Merz (TUB), Mona Marill (AUS)

ABSTRACT

The deliverable report presents the results of task 4.6 *Site control dashboard and Visualization*. The purpose of the document is to present the visualization and real-time control dashboard of the ASHVIN DT platform to manage construction site activities. Primarily, the report introduces different visualization routines implemented on the ASHVIN platform to facilitate construction site control. Furthermore, the application and the development of the site control & KPI dashboards for different demo construction sites of the ASHVIN project are presented as well.

KEYWORDS

Dashboard, Visualization, KPIs

REVISIONS

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
V0.1	14.03.2023	Draft	DTT
V0.2	16.03.2023	Review	AUS
V0.3	22.03.2023	Review	TUB
V0.4	28.03.2023	Review	TUB
V1.0	31.03.2023	Submission	DTT

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ACRONYMS & DEFINITIONS

AECO	Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operation
BIM	Building information model
CMT	Configuration management tool
DT	Digital twin
DES	Discrete Event Simulation
DTC	Digital twin construction
IoT	Internet of Things
KPIs	Key performance indicators
PIs	Performance indicators
PPC	Percentage plan complete
WP	Work package

ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collect real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behavior of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualization methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security / privacy.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The deliverable report is part of work package (WP) 4 of the ASHVIN project titled “Control and real-time simulation of construction”. The WP aims to improve the management and control of construction site activities using digital twin (DT). This deliverable addresses T4.6: *Site control dashboard & Visualization*, which intends to describe the interactive dashboard for the ASHVIN DT platform to facilitate construction management.

1.1 Background

A construction project is a labor-intensive undertaking that needs to be delivered in a timely manner and within budget. According to a study by (ENR, 2005), 90% of the time in construction meetings is devoted to describing the platform, explaining the rationale of decisions, and evaluating goals whereas only 10% of the time is spent on real decision-making such as the discussion about what-if scenarios. Therefore, operations planning is a vital component of managing and controlling the different aspects of an ongoing construction project. Measurement and assessment of project performance is an integral part of control for construction projects. Such projects have associated with them large data sets, comprised of data collected to represent construction status constantly.

To achieve this the project stakeholders, need to have visibility and access to accurate data to make the right decision at the right time. Visual analytics can provide a means of analyzing data from various dimensions of a project to extract information to aid decision making and help explain reasons for performance to date (Russell et al., 2009). Project Dashboards utilizing information technology for the representation of the construction process and progress introduce a different paradigm for project management to the project stakeholders (Song et al., 2005).

1.2 Objective and Intended Audience

The research work presented in the report aims to effectively communicate construction progress information through a site-control dashboard of the construction sites. Additionally, the dashboard provides visualization of performance metrics and the sensor data from the construction site to generate the Key performance indicators (KPI) graphs in near real-time.

The target audience for this deliverable is project and construction managers, construction companies, and public stakeholders/clients. The ASHVIN dashboard as a simple visualization tool can be beneficial for both blue-collar and white-collar workers. Also, the work presented in this deliverable promotes the use of digital twin based control of construction sites to encourage the architecture, engineering, construction & operation (AECO) industry to propel the digitization of the industry.

1.3 Existing solutions

Among the current construction management market solutions, there is widespread use of visualization and dashboards although traditionally construction visualization was prepared by hand sketches, diagrams, technical drawings, and 3D renderings. In recent years, several start-ups and construction management software products have emerged on the market that offer Internet of Things (IoT) platforms for real-time data visualizations and dashboards. The 3D Repo cloud-based platform for BIM data

management offers Power BI templates to produce an automatically generated dashboard report which summarises model quality and highlights non-conformities (3D Repo, 2022). The construction management system developed by WeBuild (WeBuild, 2022) provides commercial contractors complete control over their projects by providing real-time dashboards and summary reports for the full visibility of WeBuild's tools. It provides executive & project dashboards along with company reports for complete control. Sitemate offers Dashpivot as one of its products to facilitate real-time project dashboards by pulling data from the forms being filled out in the field automatically. Thus, enabling the use of accurate and up-to-date data for the monitoring and tracking of construction projects (Sitemate, 2022). Lyndon solution provides Construction Viz (Lydon Solutions, 2022) to manage construction projects by enabling the user to see dashboards., KPIs and one-click reports that can be integrated into Microsoft 365 and SharePoint for enhancing overall project management.

Muti-purpose business intelligence (BI) software offers solutions for construction projects as well. For instance, InetSoft (InetSoft, 2022) provides interactive visualization dashboards for all construction analytics with KPIs and reporting requirements of executives and stakeholders alike. Similarly, DataPine offers professional BI dashboards for a visually appealing presentation of analysis results and relevant KPIs to guarantee an effective information flow to provide data-driven decisions at any time.

1.4 Outline

The deliverable is structured in six sections. The first section introduces the background and purpose of the deliverable report. In the following section, the relevant literature research for the concerned topic is presented. Subsequently, section 3 presents the different visualizations implemented on the ASHVIN DT platform for the various demo sites. In addition, section 4 presents the developed dashboard for particular use cases to control construction sites based on daily insights. Section 5 presents the tool-wise KPI planning dashboards for the digital twin of the particular demo sites. Lastly, section 6 summarizes the main contributions of the work and is followed by section 7 which presents future research to build upon the work done.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Visualization

The inception of scientific visualization was marked by a national science foundation panel report in 1987 on graphics, image processing, and workstations wherein the key to visualization is defined as the ‘transformation of the symbolic into the geometric’ (McCormick et al., 1987). Representing data in a visual format “makes the human brain use more of its perceptual abilities for the initial processing of any data than relying completely on its cognitive abilities”. From the human psychology perspective through visual perception, humans are able to see, interpret and organize their environment. Hence data visualization can be extremely effective as it takes advantage of the human brain’s perception ability (TTG, 2022). From the perspective of research data, effective illustrations are vital. Visualization should be clear, concise, and complete (3 C’s of good composition) alongside fulfilling two purposes: first to visualize and explore correlations and predictions among data sets; and second, to illustrate interpretations of these data clearly and concisely to an audience (Schultz, 2018).

Around 25 years back a lot of underlying research was done into graphical algorithms, yet the visualization of results took days or weeks. However, visualization is having a renaissance recently driven to an extent, by huge improvements in GPU processing power and DTs can be natural extensions to the visualization (Siemens, 2020).

2.2 Visualization in Digital twins

A DT represents the current status of a physical, dynamic, entity that provides explicit and useful knowledge for decision making. To achieve this, the digital twin must transform complex data into useful and understandable visualizations. Thus, the visualization of the digital twin is essential for the real-time representation of the physical counterpart (Zhu et al., 2019a). Depending on the characteristics of DT data, the visualization can be in different forms.

Visualization technologies are of the essence for real-time monitoring of physical assets and processes as the study by (Qi et al., 2021) presents a data-driven digital twin lifecycle that includes data collection, transmission, storage, processing, fusion, and visualization. The data visualization technologies vary depending on the applications and DT data visualization provides neat, intuitive, and clear data information to personnel for real-time monitoring and rapid capture of target information. In the case of data visualization, for instance, open-source software Echarts can run smoothly on PCs and browsers alongside similar tools presented in Figure 1. Although in this case the data visualization is primarily considered for graphical data, the data can be required to be visualized in different forms as well.

Figure 1: Tools for digital twin data management (Qi et al., 2021)

Different visualizations apply to different use cases based on the type of technology have been used to achieve solutions for problems such as the following. Using the 3D twin model, the development of a digital twin-based detailed and real-time data-driven 3D visualization monitoring traceability of a continuous casting machine through IoT sensors helps to manage the service life cycle and maintenance of the machine (Han et al., 2020). (Auganix, 2021) introduced an AR digital twin for the mining industry by incorporating and visualizing mine planning data with the physical environment to offer a cohesive solution for optimizing the cost, errors, and productivity of the mining process. The study by (Dembski et al., 2019) presented a collaborative visualization environment in VR for the digital twin to provide a potential solution for urban planning alongside citizen participation for the city of Herrenberg in Germany.

2.2.1 Visualization for Construction Digital twins

Visualization of construction activities has gained increasing credibility in recent years and has been considered as one of the four main IT domains in construction (Behzadan, 2008). In the case of the AECO sector, data is generally gathered from heterogeneous sources (requirements, schedules, simulations, sensors, etc) that have to be correlated to the existing BIM models, ensure consistency across project models and documentation along with the temporal dimension (Boje et al., 2020). In recent years several visualization approaches have been explored for the control and planning of sites during the construction phase. Although some of the research did not consider real-time visualization/simulation, from the perspective visualization of construction DTs real-time or near real-time visualization would be essential.

To improve construction safety (Cheng & Teizer, 2013) developed a framework for streaming data from real-time positioning sensors to a real-time data visualization platform in a simulated virtual construction site. (Rohani et al., 2014) categorize visualization of construction processes as activity-based visualization (4D CAD) and operation-based visualization planning through the use of VR and AR to enable comprehensive construction management. Likewise, researchers (Fard & Peña-Mora, 2007) developed a semi-automated system for visualization of progress monitoring based on vision-based approaches and through different visualization techniques.

Research by (Reinbold et al., 2022) explored the implementation of digital visual management (DVM) for Finnish construction sites by comparing it with currently used analog visual management devices to improve the flow of updated information to construction crews during task execution.

Therefore, for the development of digital twin construction (DTC), the workflow is based on DT information systems to implement data-driven planning and control for the construction of buildings and civil infrastructure. DTC information requires appropriate data visualization tools to communicate the project status, deviations from the design intent or production plan, and any other anomalies (Sacks et al., 2020)

2.3 Dashboard for Digital twins

The concept of digital twins can be traced back to use by NASA in the 1960s during the first trips to the moon. NASA built exact replicas of everything that was launched into space. Prior to sending instructions to the astronauts by mission control, simulations were made to what could be called an “Analog Twin” to simulate decisions made before implementing them on the physical object thousands of kilometers away. Mission control (Figure 2) could be considered a dashboard for the mission wherein all data was displayed and used to monitor and verify the status of the mission in real-time. At that time with the available technology, the dashboard required the space of an auditorium (Fink & Mata, 2019).

Figure 2: NASA mission control dashboard (NASA, 2018)

Digital twin is also used in Formula 1 racing to simulate the performance of the car to produce the best possible prototypes. Additionally, the DT enables the technicians and engineers sitting remotely in the pit to simulate and monitor the stresses on the car in real-time, while the car is driving at 300 km/h on the track to ensure the car is performing at the highest level possible. Figure 3 illustrates the digital twin dashboard for the F1 cars.

Figure 3: Vodafone McLaren Mercedes dashboard (Bognar, 2014)

The National Aquatics Center, also known as Water Cube, was one of the most iconic venues of the 2008 Beijing Olympic Games. Wherein ARUP had to develop a digital twin platform for smart facility management for the 2022 Winter Olympics. As shown in Figure 4 the dashboard for the pilot BIM + IoT + Analytics digital twin platform that provides insight into the operation of future sport venues (Arup, 2019).

Figure 4: Dashboard for the DT of Water Cube (Arup, 2019)

(Harode & Thabet, 2022) developed a low-level DT that allows visualization and monitoring of five key parameters to measure air quality in a healthcare facility operating room suite. Data captured from sensors and simulations are transmitted to the digital twin PowerBI dashboard as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: DT dashboard to monitor air quality parameters in an operating room (Harode & Thabet, 2022)

2.3.1 Digital Twin Construction Dashboards

The application of DT's during construction requires asset data so that the as-planned and as-built stages can be merged. Any changes (captured by images, videos, and point clouds) during construction can be merged into the virtual representation. Additionally, the sensing layer (e.g. sensors, IoT devices, and the asset management system) is installed as part of the physical asset and replicated on the virtual representation (Seaton et al., 2022).

(Rogage et al., 2022) visualized their construction project on Aquila built on Autodesk Forge viewer to enable an interactive visual dashboard that can be accessed on a web browser. The dashboard provides an overview of program progress and resource utilization. Earthwork equipment resources of a site can be viewed on its geographical representation, which is created by embedding the site BIM model in the MapBox API as illustrated in Figure 6. In addition, sensor data from the monitored earthwork equipment are used to create an overview of the entire project, the resources, and the activity performance. An AI4ACM dashboard (Figure 7) is created within Google Data Studio for easy visualization of data insights. Four key areas of data insights are revealed from the data: the earthwork equipment utilization ratio, the task status, the equipment distance and time, and the speed distribution. Therefore, the availability of a user-driven experience is essential for DTs to deliver the necessary requirements and engage with end-users to enable holistic decision-making (Boje et al., 2020).

Figure 6: Resource utilization (Rogage et al., 2022)

Figure 7: AI engines insights dashboard (Rogage et al., 2022)

3 ASHVIN VISUALIZATIONS

This section presents the visualization routines implemented for the ASHVIN DT platform with a brief overview of the benefits of different types of visualizations for construction projects.

3.1 Sensor data visualization

A construction project's database is voluminous, containing data that varies from textual form to quantitative data and cost breakdowns. However, with the application of DT's real-time gathers represents the construction site as a virtual entity. One of the ways of visualization and representation is through real-time data collected from sensors alongside historical data (Zhu et al., 2019b).

The ASHVIN DT platform has the feature to display near real-time sensor measurements installed at the construction site. The sensors installed at the different demonstration sites measure different values during the construction process such as stress, strain, environmental values, cameras, etc. The measured data is sent to ASHVIN's IoT platform. Subsequently, the ASHVIN DT platform is integrated with the IoT platform to gather the measured data. Figure 8 shows one of the sensor data visualizations on the platform for structural measurements during the construction process.

Figure 8: Graphical data visualization

3.2 3D visualization

The use of 3D visualizations essentially visualizes what is not built yet, therefore aiding in communication and displaying construction ideas for adequate discussion by the stakeholders (Hartmann et al., 2008). Traditional 3D CAD models defined a facility with independent 3D views, such as plans, sections, and elevations with only graphical entities such as lines, arcs, and circles. BIM employing the 3D model to generate 3D

visualizations integrates semantically rich information related to the facility, including geometric and functional properties (Ding et al., 2014). BIM-based 3D visualization of the construction site can provide potential end users by offering solutions in several ways. 3D visualization can serve as an interface with the real-world construction site by allowing users to compare the as-designed/as-planned model with the as-built model/condition to avoid constructability errors. Additionally, 3D visualizations can reduce clashes between existing and new building objects through the application of 3D clash detection (Voordijk & Scholtenhuis, 2022).

On the ASHVIN DT platform, the 3D visualizations are based on the BIM file of the particular demo site. Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the 3D visualizations of the construction site for Demo#1 Bridges for High-speed railways in Spain and Demo#6 Office Buildings in Spain respectively. The DT platform can visualize/render any type of 3D model (bridge or building) as the ASHVIN project includes different types of civil engineering projects.

Figure 9: 3D Visualization Demo#1

Figure 10: 3D Visualization Demo#6

3.3 4D visualization

4D visualization is developed in a virtual environment based on 4D modeling integrating time (i.e., the temporal dimension) with the 3D models (i.e., spatial

dimensions), thus representing information over both space and time (Fischer et al., 2003). Construction planning is a collaborative and iterative process and as projects shift towards integrated delivery, 4D visualization offers a common understanding of how information is represented. As such 4D visualizations during the construction phase can boost the planning, facilitate time-space conflict, support automated progress tracking, and provide a clearer view of the construction process (Hamledari et al., 2018). Additionally, the use of the 4D model eases the identification of errors such as inconsistency in the level of detail of the schedule, missing activities in the schedule, and logic of the schedule. Thus, 4D visualizations enable the engineer to visualize planning information preventing the need for conceptualization and a simple understanding of problems associated with the construction planning process (Alzarrad et al., 2021).

For the 4D visualization on the ASHVIN DT platform, the 3D models are linked to the construction sequence to generate 4D construction simulations which can be simulated using the playback panel as depicted in Figure 11. Moreover, the DT platform has a feature that compares two 4D construction simulations of the same 3D model through a split-screen function (Figure 12).

Figure 11: 4D construction sequence visualization Demo#6

Figure 12: Comparison of different 4D construction simulations

3.4 Simulations

Visualization of simulation data through the modeling process is vital for understanding and tuning the model behavior. Therefore, the visualization of modeling and simulation is critical to represent the simulation and its outputs in the context of the real-world system that is modeled (Vernon-Bido et al., 2015). With the widespread implementation of digital twins, simulations can be done almost real-time for data from IoT sources, such as stresses and strains by linking of simulation to real-time performance data, and hence visualizations will continue to be more important to see and understand results & observations (Newton, 2017).

Simulation-based methods are developed on the ASHVIN DT for the early planning of construction activities and supply chain logistics. Additionally, the simulation-based planning tool aims to proactively address construction safety issues. Subsequently, the different simulation-based visualizations for construction management are presented below:

3.4.1 Concrete consolidation quality

For the Configuration Management Tool (CMT) of WP 4 simulation is done for the estimation of vibration quality of concrete columns based on real-time tracking. The measurements are done for formwork acceleration of columns during the vibration of concrete. Simulation visualization is depicted in Figure 13 which shows the vibration quality by highlighting the columns as per quality based on the vibration time, with red color indicating bad quality and green representing good quality. Additionally, the CMT tool allows for visualization of DT sensor data measurements to be represented (see Figure 14) graphically with acceleration over time graphs for the respective highlighted columns.

Figure 13: Simulation of concrete consolidation quality

Figure 14: Simulation with attributed DT data for quality control

3.4.2 Asset management

Simulation of asset management during the construction process is developed under the CMT tool. Wherein the quality of product installations during construction is assessed whether it is as per requirements based on the DT data. The selected floor for demonstration is the 16th floor which serves as a hotel. Figure 15 illustrates the simulation for as-built and as-designed model comparisons of demo#5, to compare as-intended vs as-installed information types.

Figure 16 depicts the verification of the parameters for one of the curtain walls. The comparison is done between what is intended at the site (as-designed) and what is actually installed at the site (as-built). For the curtain walls, the aspect of thermal bridges is important and has an impact on the building's performance.

Figure 15: Simulation of as-planned vs as-built models

Figure 16: Simulation with attributed DT data for asset management

3.4.3 Installation of prefabricated columns

For the Discrete Event Simulation (DES) tool the simulation formalizes the work process pattern mounting of prefabricated columns of an industrial building. The simulation is based on DT data (time-lapsed images) to explore the possibility of different simulation options for the planning of mounting 70 columns as shown in Figure 17, the column is highlighted in red on an empty floor space to simulate the mounting process. Additionally, the tool also enables the simulation of mounting sequence for construction planning as illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 17: Simulation of mounting of columns activity

Figure 18: Simulation for work process based on data collection

3.4.4 Finishing works

The DES tool enables simulation that is developed for the planning of finishing works on the 16th floor of the KINEUM building. Each activity has a certain colour assigned, and the different workspaces are highlighted in the relevant colour spanning the duration of the particular activity (Figure 19). Therefore, the flow of the different trades over the various workspaces displayed over time will aid in the coordination for the successful execution of finishing works and avoid time-space conflicts.

Figure 19: Simulation for construction finishing activities

4 SITE CONTROL DASHBOARD

The ASHVIN DT site control Dashboard for the demo cases is developed to provide the construction manager or the responsible site personnel with an update on the construction and the associated construction management processes based on DT data measurements and capture technologies installed/used at the construction site. As the previous section elaborated on the different visualization routines implemented on the ASHVIN DT platform, this section builds upon the visualizations for the dashboard development. The dashboard is developed and applied on the ASHVIN demo sites for the use cases of issue management and construction progress monitoring of construction activities.

4.1 Issue Management Dashboard

The issue management dashboard is developed for Demo#6 Office Building in Spain, with the purpose of providing a detailed synopsis of the issues generated during the construction phase of the project. Figure 20 gives an overview of the dashboard for the use case of issue management which allows displaying data in the form of graphical and 3D visualizations.

In terms of features of the dashboard, it contains the generated issue list on the top left corner with the associated parameters such as the assigned person and the status of the issue. The issues are linked to their assigned 3D objects in the BIM model by the issue-generating person. When the user selects an issue from the list, they are redirected to the location of the 3D object in the BIM model, the issue can be assigned to any type of 3D object as shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22. Furthermore, in the BIM model, the user can navigate using the zoom and rotate functions to get a view of the created issue as needed. Another dashboard feature is the issue relation visualizer, which visualizes a created issue with the assigned personnel and their work designations along with other assigned personnel for that issue. For example, as illustrated in Figure 23 the Main Contractor named Maple Cross is assigned an issue along with other stakeholders for the same issue. Lastly, the dashboard has the feature to graphically visualize the different issues created by issue type, by status (open, closed & in progress), and by priority (low, medium & high).

The ASHVIN issue management dashboard based on DT data gathered from the site enables the construction manager to understand what issues are present, what objects they belong to, when they should be resolved and the responsible person to resolve them. Thus, eradicating to some extent, the delays and clashes caused by the generated issues and thus saving resources in terms of time, cost, and material. Additionally, it provides insight into possible issues during execution that can be used as a reference that is to be avoided as early as the planning phase of future construction projects.

Figure 20: Issue management control dashboard

Figure 21: Column Formwork issue linked to the 3D object in the BIM model

Figure 22: Staircase issue linked to the 3D object in the BIM model

Figure 23: Issue relations visualizer with encircled relation b/w the person and their designation

4.2 Progress Monitoring Dashboard

Additionally, a construction progress monitoring dashboard is developed for Demo#4 industrial building in Germany to facilitate construction site control by tracking the construction progress on a regular basis and through real-time input directly from the construction site. The dashboard as depicted in Figure 24¹, provides an overview of the use case of construction progress monitoring with a list of completed assets, the linked 3D model, and a camera feed from the construction site.

The developed dashboard has features to ensure practical tracking of construction progress to be updated on a daily basis based on input from the site. The asset list (Figure 25) provides a summary of the different objects/building elements with their completion date and the status with green indicating as completed and red indicating not completed. Figure 25 and Figure 26 manifest the asset (building element) and the link to the as-built BIM model, when the user selects the asset, they are redirected to the location of the 3D object in the BIM model with elements completed (already constructed) on the current date in green and the one's due to be constructed in red. Moreover, in the BIM model, the user can navigate using the zoom and rotate functions to get a holistic view of the as-built construction in the 3D model. The update from the site is through the construction site webcam as represented in Figure 27¹. Currently, the dashboard shows the images from the site at the end of the construction routine on a daily basis. When the user opens the dashboard, it shows the latest site camera image from yesterday's end of construction routine, and using the arrow button the user can access images from previous days to assess construction progress along with the as-built visualization.

Figure 28 provides the visualization for the percentage plan complete (PPC) i.e., is one of the established ASHVIN performance indicators (Łukaszewska, 2021). By measuring the reliability of a construction schedule ($PPC = \text{Activities completed as planned} / \text{Total activities planned}$) where the typical interval for PPC calculation is a week of activities. The PPC is updated on the dashboard based on input from the site as illustrated in Figure 28, the PPC of the week before, and the latest PPC. Additionally, the dashboard contains categorized task lists (Figure 29) for completed, delayed, and tasks that have been stopped. The task list is created at the initial project stage and it changes during the construction phase thus being updated on the dashboard to keep the construction manager informed.

The ASHVIN construction progress monitoring dashboard based on a real-time camera installed at the site to monitor the site progress provides an output for tracking progress and assess productivity based on indicators such as percentage plan complete. Additionally linking the dashboard to the construction schedule would reduce the gap between reality and plan by minimizing scheduling risks and facilitating the construction manager to generate reports on the percentage complete, quantities installed, rate of work, and estimated completion dates. Therefore, the developed dashboard provides extensive progress tracking data with practicality at its core by using near real-time digital twin data feed from the construction sites and helping the construction companies keep on schedule and within budget.

¹ Construction Site Webcam panel is left empty due to data privacy requirements

Figure 24: Construction progress monitoring control dashboard

Figure 25: Mounted column and the as-built 3D model visualization

Figure 26: Not mounted column and the as-built 3D model visualization

Figure 27: Near real-time DT data from the construction site

Figure 28: PPC visualization as a performance indicator (left: current status and right: previous status)

Figure 29: Task list for industrial building construction (Demo#4)

5 DEMOSITES-KPI DASHBOARD

The previous section presents the control dashboard to control construction sites on a daily basis based on DT input, the KPI dashboard facilitates the planning of construction activities. The section presents the implementation of the ASHVIN dashboard on the real-life demo sites of the project for the planning of construction site activities. The KPI dashboards are presented as per the toolkit based implementation of the demo construction sites for WP4. Table 1 summarizes the KPI dashboard developed for various demo construction sites, of which some are described in the subsequent sections.

Table 1: KPI Dashboard Implementation

Demo	Tools	Phase
#4 Industrial Building, Germany	DES	Construction
#5 Kineum Office Building, Gothenburg, Sweden	CMT & DES	Construction
#6 Office Building, Barcelona, Spain	CMT & DES	Construction
#10 Quay Wall, Rotterdam, Nederland	4DV-C	Construction

5.1 #4 Industrial Building construction in Germany

The demo site is an industrial building located in, Germany. The building is purposed as a state-of-the-art production facility to ensure a Smart Factory as depicted in Figure 30. The industrial building has an area of almost 30,000 m² and a height of 12 meters. It consists of four different halls, with halls 1 & 2 forming one part of the building to be used for the production of food packaging along with halls 3 & 4 forming the other part for storage and logistics. The structure primarily consists of prefabricated components such as precast concrete columns, steel walls, sandwich panels, and steel roof panels.

Figure 30: Visualization of the DC#4 industrial hall (Spies, 2022)

5.1.1 DES - Monitoring of Prefabricated Columns

The ASHVIN discrete event simulation (DES) tool simulates construction work patterns to test different construction possibilities by changing supply chain logistics, resource allocation, and site layouts (Jungmann, 2022). Based on real-time DT data from a high-definition webcam monitoring the construction execution, the site measurements are analyzed by machine learning to gain reliable stochastic productivity information. The DES tool formalizes the work process pattern for the mounting of prefabricated columns by a mobile crane. The tool simulates the delivery of columns through trucks as per the departure time and delivery intervals taking into account the available construction resources & costs for simulating the activity of mounting of columns.

The DES tool was applied for the planning of mounting 70 columns and visualized on the ASHVIN DT platform, creating different construction scenarios (simulations) based on user inputs and real-time data from cameras. Additionally, the KPIs are calculated through the tool and uploaded to the tool dashboard as illustrated in Figure 31 to compare the estimated KPIs through bar charts and a spider diagram for different construction simulations. The DES tool KPI dashboard has features to enable the user to plan construction site activities based on the real-time DT data (Figure 32 and Figure 33) to facilitate the comparison of different construction sequences that results in productive, resource-efficient, and safer construction execution.

Figure 31: DES-Demo#4 dashboard

Figure 32: Dashboard-based comparison and control for the DES tool Demo#4

Figure 33: Spider chart for comparison based on PIs

5.2 #5 Kineum office building in Sweden

The Kineum case (see Figure 34) is a high-rise building located in the city of Gothenburg, Sweden. The construction project started in 2019 and ended last summer, 2022. The building consists of 30,000 m² and has 27 floors. It has a height of 110 meters and it is used to host office spaces and hotel accommodations. The developed KPI dashboard for the DES tool implemented on the Kineum demo site is explained in the subsequent section

Figure 34: Construction of the Kineum project in Sweden (NCC, 2021)

5.2.1 DES – Finishing Works

The DES tool illustrates the work process pattern finishing works based on nine different activities. For each activity, the respective workspace and the related trades have to be able to start. If the workspace or the trade is occupied, the relevant activity has to wait until resources are released. The first activity is the drywall construction on one side by drywall constructors. Hereafter, ventilation, plumbing, and electricity are installed in the wall by HVAC, plumbing, and electrical trades. In general, the whole procedure can be applied to different workspaces so that works are executed simultaneously. The collection of real-time data was not possible and hence for the finishing works processes pattern the Probability density function (PDF) is based on assumptions.

The KPIs are calculated through the tool and visualized graphically on the tool dashboard as illustrated in Figure 35 to compare different construction simulations. The visualizations are done through the bar (Figure 36) and spider charts to compare the different construction options as per the associated performance parameters to choose the most optimal option as per the user requirements. The DES tool KPI dashboard supports the better planning of finishing works by coordinating different trades to avoid time-space conflict.

Figure 35: DES-Demo#5 dashboard

Figure 36: PIs comparison for Demo#5 for finishing activities

5.3 #10 Quay wall in the Netherlands

The concerned Euromax quay wall is part of the port of Rotterdam which is the largest port in Europe and one of the biggest in the world. The construction of the Euromax Quay Wall was carried out from 2017 to 2019 (see Figure 37). Port of Rotterdam aims to develop intelligent infrastructure and one of the key structures identified are the smart quay walls. The quay wall structure has varied DT measurements including displacement of retaining walls, strains in the anchor piles, strains in the axially loaded piles, and loads on the fenders.

Figure 37: Construction of quay wall (Duffy & Gavin, 2022)

5.3.1 4DV-C Construction Sequence

The 4DV-C tool visualizes past construction activities based on activities tracked through DT data. The tool enables planning by simulating future construction sequences and site layout options. The 3D model is linked with the construction schedule/sequence to create 4D visualizations.

The 4DV-C tool was applied for Demo#10 to simulate the construction sequence of one of the quay walls. Figure 38 illustrates the 3D model of the construction site alongside the calculated KPIs in the tool dashboard. The KPIs associated with the 4DV-C tool are visualized to enable better planning and management of the construction process as shown in Figure 39. As generally quay wall construction is done in phases, *Productivity* KPI represents phase-wise construction e.g., on one section the piles are being installed while on the other the diaphragm wall. Additionally, the *Resource Efficiency* KPI presents the material consumption through PI such as grout consumed and lost casings during the installation of piles.

Figure 38: 4DV-C-Demo#10 dashboard

Figure 39: KPIs and PIs-based dashboard Demo#10

The 4DV-C tool KPI dashboard supports better planning and control of construction activities for quay wall construction. For instance, during the piling process if there are any deviations, this could mean that the soil conditions are different from what was initially expected and therefore the pile’s capacity could also be different. This needs to be flagged and the initial pile capacity predictions might need to be revised if the deviation is significant enough.

6 CONCLUSION

Visualization can play multi-faceted roles in the construction industry, as the construction team uses visual data to guide their operations, plan resources, and manage overall coordination. Therefore, the ASHVIN DT Platform³ implements visualization and real-time control dashboard to control and plan construction site activities. The developed ASHVIN control dashboard linked with near real-time digital twin data from the construction site aims to communicate on a daily basis to the construction manager the project status, divergence from the intended design or the production plan and any other possible anomalies affecting the construction activities. Furthermore, the developed KPIs dashboard intends to provide information based on ascertained parameters (KPI and PI) to aid in the planning of future construction processes.

In terms of limitations, the dashboard currently does assess the status of performance indicators at the current stage of construction (e.g.: what is the resource efficiency and productivity at the current stage of construction) due to limitations in terms of data collection from the demo sites. Also, the dashboard does not integrate all the sensor measurements which can be accessed using individual tools of the DT platform.

7 OUTLOOK

With respect to further development, certain considerations to improve the dashboard functionality for better construction site control are as follows:

- Development of user based customizable dashboards to cater to different stakeholders of construction projects as requirements such as generating reports.
- Improve the dashboard UI such as creating a multi-docking feature for the different dashboard windows/panels.
- Possibility of integration of business intelligence tools such as PowerBI/Grafana for better visualization and use of project data metrics.
- Validation of developed KPIs to provide better insights for dashboard visualizations.
- Further integration of additional DT data, especially imagery-based data such as point cloud scans.

³ <https://ashvin-integration.digitaltwin.technology/Demo/>

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